

The Influence of Social Media on Academic Performance of Undergraduate Students of College of Education, Zing, Taraba State, Nigeria

Suleh, Bala Albert (Ph.D)¹ & Chigbu, Eberechukwu Fransisca (Ph.D)²

¹Department of General Studies, Taraba State Polytechnic, Suntai
Email-balaalbertsule@gmail.com
08037329599

²Department of Guidance and Counseling, Faculty of Education,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka
ef.chigbu@unizik.edu.ng
08100435102

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5494506>

Abstract

The study examines the influence of social media on academic performance of undergraduate students 'college of education, zing, Taraba state. Quantitative survey method was adopted for the study. The population consists of 5000 undergraduate students. The study made use of Taro Yame's formula to sample 100 students. Questionnaires were employed as the instrument for data collection. The questionnaire was administered to 100 randomly selected students. The entire questionnaires administered were duly filled and retrieved given a high response rate of 100%. The gamut of this study is on the uses and gratification theory. Data collected were coded and analyzed on SPSS version 22 and presented in tables. Findings revealed that students of college of education have access to the internet and that they do so through different mediums such as smart phones, tablets and computers. The studies also postulate that students who spend more time on social media are likely to perform poorly in their academic activities than those who do not. The study recommends that students should decrease their introduction to social media and give careful consideration to their studies. Students, particularly those ready to record gigantic scholarly achievement should guard themselves against the successive utilization of social media.

Key words: Influence, Social media, Academic performance, Students, College of education

Introduction

There is enormous celebration on the planet today because of the imminent and change in the communication pattern which has helped the scope of communication by means of Information and communication technology (ICTs). Ufuophu and Ayobami (2012:129) observe that the ICTs include internet, satellite, cable data transmission and computer assisted equipment. Social network is a social

structure made up of individuals' or organizations called "nodes", which are tied (connected) by one or more specific types of interdependency, such as friendship, kinship, common interest, financial exchange, dislike, sexual relationships or relationships of beliefs, knowledge or prestige.

Social media has emerged to be one of the most vital communication means. It exists so as to ease communication among people regardless of the expanse, making it open to people to easily share information, files and pictures and videos, create blogs and send messages, and conduct real-time conversations. These systems are referred to as social, simply because they allow communication with friends, course mates, teachers, project supervisors, lecturers etc. so easily and effectively. Social media which are a form of electronic communication that has become the highest activity on the internet. According to Kim and Kim, (2010) "Social media are the emerging digital communication channels which create a user oriented information sharing ground where any people can generate or subscribe information content as both information provider and consumer". Better, (2016) sees social media as "computer mediated tools that allow people or companies to create, share exchange information, career interest, ideas, pictures/virtual communities and networks "By suggestion, through Social media, individuals can with no much of a stretch trade profitable information which can enhance their profession interest, thoughts and so on.

It additionally helps in sending pictorial outlines of thoughts. Andreas and Micheal (2010) asserts that "social media is a group of internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of web 2.0 and that allow the creation and exchange of user generated content". Kietzmann and Hermkens (2011) elaborates on this, stating that "social media depends on Mobile and Web-based technologies to create highly interactive platforms through which individuals and communities share, co-create, discuss, and modify user-generated content. They introduce substantial and pervasive changes to communications between communities and individuals". In contribution, Ganiyu, and Akinreti, (2011) assert that "the emergence of social media has increase interactivity among people, making them to be producers and consumers of information in a simultaneous manner". Social media such as Facebook, Twitter, 2go etc. have brought tremendous improvement in the communication system which enhances learning, it has provided different entertainment functions which serve as a tool for social change and fast exchange of information. With the aid of the internet students can form their own page, access to news and lectures notes via email sent to him/her(them)by a lecturer.

An additional benefit of social technologies provided on the internet is that they are frequently free or require marginal investment, eliminating a potential barrier to adoption (Brown, 2010).

There has been various overview and opinions which recognized four major advantages of social media use in higher education.

These include, enhancing relationship, improving learning motivation, offering personalized course material, and developing collaborative abilities. This means that social networking activities have the possibility of enhancing student contact and is used to improve their participation in class, particularly where introverted students are involved. Students can function in online group learning with less or no anxiety of needs to raise questions before peers in school (Wheeler, Yeomans, and Wheeler, 2008). Consequentially, social media has its disadvantages which include: lack of emotional connection, decreases face to face communication skills, conveys inauthentic expression of feelings, diminishes understanding and thoughtfulness, facilitates laziness, creates a skewed self image, reduces family closeness, and causes distraction (Mitchell, 2021). In agreement to the above assertion, Vanessa (2021), insist that social media has its ability to distract students from learning and adversely affect their academic studies. In lieu of the above controversies, the use of Social networking sites has raised dust among researchers. Some see it as distraction to learning for the student as it involves multitasking, while others attest to the potentials of Social networking sites. Against this backdrop this study examined the influence of social media that have on student's academic performance with specific reference to college of education students.

Statement of the Problem

Since the initiation of social media sites in the 1990s, it is understood that in many part of the world the academic performance of students is facing a lot of neglect and challenges. There is a divergence, interruption and alienated attention between social networking activities and their academic work. It is pragmatic that students dedicate more attention to social media than they do to their studies. Asemah, Okpanachi and Edegoh,(2013) describe this situation stating that “it is a common sight to see a youth chatting in sensitive and highly organized places like church, mosque and lecture venues. Some are so carried away that even as they are walking along the high way, they keep chatting”.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

- (i) Do you use social media networks?
- (ii) What are the social media networks that you are more exposed to?
- (iii) What is the influence of social media on your academic performance?

Methods

This study adopted quantitative survey research design. The study area is college Zing. The population of this study is the entire students of college of education, zing who are about 5000 (Source: admission office 2020). To determine the sample of this study the Taro Yamane’s formula will be adopted as follows:

$N = N$

.....

$1 + N (e)^2$

Where: N = sample size sought

e = Level of error (0.10) ²

N = Population size 5000

$N = 5000$

$1 + 5000 (0.10)^2$

$N = 5000$

$1 + 5000 (0.01)$

$N = 5000$

51

$N = 100$

Therefore, the sample for this study is 100 respondents who were randomly selected from the four faculties in college of education, zing, namely: Arts and Social sciences, Sciences, and Agriculture education respectively.

The sampling technique adopted for this study is simple random sampling technique in which each member of the sample is given an equal chance of being selected (Yates, David and Daren 2008). The study employed questionnaire in gathering the data. The data collected were coded in SPSS version22 and

analyzed using descriptive statistics with reference to devices such as tables, frequency counts and simple percentages.

Results

Respondents' details:

Findings from the data gathered revealed that 60 (60%) out of the 100 respondents are female and 40(40%) are male and 45 (45%) out of the 100 respondents fall under the ages of 18-24, 30(30%) out of the 100 respond entail under the ages of 25-31, while 15 (15%) fall under the ages of 32-38 and 10(10%) fall under the ages of 39 and above.

This implies that most of the respondents fall under the ages of 23-25.

Research Question One: *Do you use social media networks?*

To answer this question, items 3, 4 and 6 was used from the questionnaire.

Table 1 Respondents access to the internet. Do you have access to the internet?

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
(a) YES	100	100%
(b) NO	0	0%
Total	100	100%

Source: Field Survey. College of Education 2021.

Table 1 above reveals that all the respondents have access to the internet. The question now is what medium they use to access the internet. The next question answers the various mediums used by the respondents to access the internet.

Table 2 Medium of accessing the internet. Which of the following medium do you use to access the internet?

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
(a)Computer	25	25%
(b)Smart phones	65	65%
(c)Tablet	10	10%
Total	100	100%

Source: Field Survey. College of Education 2021.

Table 2 above ascertained the medium used by the respondents in accessing the internet. The findings reveal that majority of the respondents 65(65%) make use of smart phones to access the internet, while 25 (22%)make us of computer, whereas, only 10 (10%) make use of tablet to access the internet.

Table 3 Social media account of respondents. Which of the social networking sites do you have an account with?

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
(a) 2go	5	5%
(b) BB chat	15	15%
(c) Facebook	50	50%
(d) my space	-	-
(e) WhatsApp	30	30%
(f) others specify	-	-
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey. College of Education 2021.

Table 3 above examined the social networking sites the respondents have account with. Findings reveal that a reasonable amount of the respondents 50 (50%) have an account with Face-book, while 30 (30%) have an account with WhatsApp, 15 (15%) have an account with BB chat, and only 5 (5%) out of the 100

respondents have an account with 2go. This finding implies that majority of the respondents have an account with Facebook rather than any other networking sites.

Research Question Two: What are the social media networks that you are more exposed of?

Items 7, 9, 10, 11 from the questionnaire answered research question two.

Table 4 Social media mostly exposed to by the respondents. Which Social Media Network are you mostly exposed to?

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
(a) 2go	5	5%
(b) BB Chart	10	10%
(c) Facebook	60	60%
(d) My space	-	-
(d) WhatsApp	25	25%
(f) Others specify	-	-
Total	100	100%

Source: Field Survey. College of Education 2021.

Table 4 above examined the type of social media the respondents are mostly exposed to. Findings show that majority of the respondents 60(60%) are more exposed to Face-book than any other networking site, while25 (25%) agreed to WhatsApp as the most exposed networking site to them, while 10 (10%) out of the 100respondents are more exposed to BB chat, whereas, only 5 (5%) are exposed to 2go. This implies that most of the respondents are more exposed to Facebook and WhatsApp than any other form of networking sites.

Table 5 Frequency of respondents surfing the internet: How often do you go online?

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
(a) Very Often	75	75%
(b) Often	15	15%
(c) Not Very Often	5	5%
(d) Not Often	5	5%
Total	100	100%

Source: Field Survey. College of Education 2021.

Tables 5 above seek to ascertain the frequency of respondents surfing the internet. Findings revealed that majority of the respondents 75(75%) agreed that they surf the internet very often, 15 (15%) surf the internet often, while 5 (5%) go online not very often and 5 (5%) not often. This implies that, most of the respondent’s go on line very often. That is, there is high frequency of respondents going online.

Table 6 Hours of respondents going online. How much time do you spend online daily?

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
(a) 6 hours and above	15	15%
(b) 4-5 hours	65	65%
(c) 3-4 hours	10	10%
(d) 2-3 hours	5	5%
(e) 1 hour or less	5	5%
Total	100	100%

Source: Field Survey. College of Education 2021.

Table 6 above reveals respondents time spent daily online. Majority of the respondents 65 (65%) spend4-5 hours surfing the internet, 15(15%) spend 6 hours and above online daily, 10 (10%) spent 3-4 hours, 5 (5%)spend 2-3 hours, while 5(5%) spend only 1 hour or less online. This implies that, most of the respondents spend lot of time online.

Table 7 Actions respondents do most on social media. Which of the action do you do most on social media?

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
1. Academic activities	15	15%
2. Sports and news	5	5%
3. Entertainment	10	10%
4. Chatting	70	70%
5. Others	-	-
Total	100	100%

Source: Field Survey. College of Education 2021.

Tables 7 explore the various actions carried out by the respondents on social media. Findings revealed that majority of the respondents 70 (70%) prefer chatting to other form of internet surfing, 15 (15%) agreed to using social media for academic purposes, 10(10%) concurred to using social media for entertainment purposes while only 5 (5%) out of the respondents make use of social media for sports and news. This implies that, most of the respondent’s chat, negating academic pursuits.

Research Question Three: What is the influence of social media on your academic performance?

Items 13-16 from the questionnaire answered research question three.

Table 8 Influence of social media on students’ academic performance:

Items	Responses	SA	A	UD	U	SD
1	College of education undergraduate students spend more time on social media than reading their books	70(70%)	15(15%)	-	10(10%)	5(5%)
2	The students now rely on social media to do their assignments without consulting other sources	5(5%)	60(60%)	5(5%)	25(25%)	5(5%)
3	Students exposure to social media have effect on their academic performance	65(65%)	15(15%)	5(5%)	10(10%)	5(5%)
4	The influence of social media on the academic performance of students is negative	75(75%)	10(10%)	-	10(10%)	5(5%)
5	The students who spend more time on social media are likely to perform poorly in their academic activities than those who do not.	80(80%)	7(7%)	5(5%)	3(3%)	5(5%)s

Source: Field Survey. College of Education 2021.

Table 8 above seeks to find out the influence social media have on students’ academic performance. Items 1 from the table above seek to find out if college of education students spends more time on social media than reading their books. 70 (70%) out of the 100 respondents strongly agreed that college of education students spend more time on social media than reading their books, 15 (15%) agreed to the same assertion,

on the other hand, 10 (10%) disagreed that college of education students spend more time on social media than reading their books while 5 (5%) strongly disagreed.

Items 2 from the table sought to find out if students now rely on social media to do their assignments without consulting other sources. 5(5%) strongly agreed that students now rely on social media to do their assignments without consulting other sources. 60 (60%) agreed that students now rely on social media to do their assignments without consulting other sources. 25 (25%) disagreed that students now rely on social media to do their assignments without consulting other sources, 5 (5%) strongly disagreed while 5 (5%) remained undecided as to whether students now rely on social media to do their assignments without consulting other sources.

Items 3 examined whether Students' exposure to social media have effect on their academic performance. Majority of the respondents 65 (65%) strongly agreed that students' exposure to social media have effect on their academic performance, 15 (15%) agreed that students' exposure to social media have effect on their academic performance, 10 (10%) disagreed that Students' exposure to social media have effect on their academic performance, while 5 (5%) strongly disagreed that students' exposure to social media have effect on their academic performance and 5 (5%) remained undecided.

Items 4 seek to ascertain if the influence of social media on the academic performance of students is negative. Majority of the respondents 75 (75%) strongly agreed that the influence of social media on the academic performance of students is negative, 10 (10%) agreed that the influence of social media on the academic performance of students is negative, 10 (10%) disagreed that the influence of social media on the academic performance of students is negative, while 5 (5%) strongly disagreed that the influence of social media on the academic performance of students is negative. This implies that to a very large extent, social media have negative influence on students' academic performance.

Items 5 sought to know whether students who spend more time on social media are likely to perform poorly in their academic activities than those who do not. Most of the respondents 80 (80%) strongly agreed that students who spend more time on social media are likely to perform poorly in their academic activities than those who do not, 7(7%) agreed that students who spend more time on social media are likely to perform poorly in their academic activities than those who do not, 3 (3%) disagreed that students who spend more time on social media are likely to perform poorly in their academic activities than those who do not, 5 strongly disagreed that students who spend more time on social media are likely to perform poorly in their academic activities than those who do not. On the contrary, 5 (5%) maintained neutrality as to whether students who spend more time on social media are likely to perform poorly in their academic activities than those who do not.

Base on the table above, one could deduce that social media have influence on student's academic performance and that influence is negative. This implies that, the continuous addiction to social media could stops students from studying their books as they will glue themselves to it rather than their books.

Discussion of major findings

In this section, the data collected from survey on the topic "The influence of Social Media on the academic performance of students will be discussed in details relating it to other scholar's work. The study reveals that all the respondents have access to the internet and that they do so through different mediums such as smart phones, tablets and computers.

Findings also reveal that smart phones are the most popular means of accessing the internet by students.

These devices are portable and allow students to carry it along at any given time.

The study examined the various social media networking sites that respondents have an account with and found out that Facebook and WhatsApp are the most conversant social media among students of college of education, zing. They would prefer to open account with Facebook and WhatsApp than any other social media form.

Therefore, majority of the respondents are more exposed to Face-book and WhatsApp than any other networking sites. That is, students of college education prefer chatting on Facebook and WhatsApp. These findings are in line with Asemah, and Edegoh, (2013) findings that shows that Facebook is the most used social media by undergraduate students of Kogi State University.

This study also reveal are in line that majority of students of college of education spend at least 4-5 hours or so daily surfing the internet. This shows that most of them go online as revealed in the study. These findings with Seyi, (2012), study which criticized seriously the obsessive attitude of Nigeria youths towards social media. It pointed out that the rate at which youths devote their quality time in chatting, calls for urgent attention.

The study further examines the various actions taken by students on social media and found out that most students prefer to chat than do any other thing on social media. This finding concurs with Seyi, (2012) who observed that “some students are always busy pinging and 2going while lectures are on rather than concentrating and this affects their academic pursuit”.

Findings of this study reveal that college of education students spend more time on social media than reading their books; this makes them rely on social media to do their assignments without consulting other sources. The study also revealed that students’ exposure to social media has effect on their academic performance and that effect is negative.

Further findings revealed on the research are that, students who spend more time on social media are likely to perform poorly in their academic activities than those who do not.

Conclusion

There is gigantic festival on the planet today because of the coming and change in the communication innovation which has helped the extent of communication by means of Information and communication technology (ICTs). In this manner, this study determines the impact of online networking on undergraduate scholastic execution with special reference to college of education, zing undergraduate. Discoveries demonstrated that an extraordinary number of undergraduate in the college of education, zing know about online networking and have entry to different interpersonal interaction locales. It is the perspective of this paper that undergraduate who invest more energy in online networking are liable to perform inadequately in their scholarly exercises than the individuals who don't, because of an extraordinary number of times spent on long range informal communication exercises, the scholastic execution of undergraduates endure misfortunes which could prompt poor execution in their studies.

Recommendations

In view of the discoveries of this study, the accompanying suggestions can be made

- i The government should consider the possibility of evolving a policy on teenagers’ exposure to social media.
- ii. Students should decrease their introduction to social media and give careful consideration to their studies.
- iii. Students, particularly those ready to record gigantic scholarly achievement should guard themselves against the successive utilization of social media.
- iv. The government, schools and other well to do people should empower hard work by remunerating effective students through grant plans and different impetuses.

References

- Adegboji, O.B. & Toyo, O. D (2006). The impact of the internet on research: the experience of Delta state university, abraha, nigeria. Library philosophy and practice 8
- Andreas, K. M. & Micheal, H (2010) user of the world, unite! The challenges and opportunities of Social Business Horizons 53 (1) 661.

- Asemah, E. S. & Edegoh, L. O. N. (2013). Influence of social media on the academic performance of the undergraduate students of kogi state university, anyigba, *Journal of research on humanities and social sciences* Vol. 3(12).
- Asogwa, C. E, Ojih, E. U & Onoja, B. I (2012) use of social networking sites and academic Performance among students of selected tertiary institutions in kogi state international *Journal of African and Asian studies*. Vol 6. Brown, S. (2010). From VLEs to learning webs. The implications of web 2.0 for learning and
- Ganiyu, M, & Akinreti, Q. (2011). *Secrets of online and multimedia journalism: A Manual for online and journalism practice in Africa*. Ibadan: emgee publishers Ltd.
- Buettner, R. (2016) Getting a Job via career oriented social networking sites: the weakness of Ties. 49th annual international conference on systems sciences. Kauai, Hawaii: IEEE. Doi:10_13140/RG.2.1.3249.2241.
- Grant, I. (2005). Young, people relationship with online marketing practices: an intrusion too Far? *Journal of marketing management*, 21(5/6), 607-623.
- Kamba, M. A (2008). The changing role of resources in Nigeria: the internet as an alternative Future to modernity. *Library philosophy and practice*.
- Ifeanyi-obi C. C. Olatunji S. O. & Akpala, J. (2014). Perceived effects of Facebook on Academic activities of agricultural students in university of port-Harcourt. *IOSR Journal of mobile computing and application*.
- Idakwo, L. (2011). *The use of social media among Nigeria youths*. Retrieved 9/7/2012 from: <http://www.slideshare.net/goldlami/the-use-of-social-media-amongnigeria-youths>
- Kietzmann, H, Jan, Kristopher hermkens (2011). Social media” get serious. Understanding The functional building blocks of social media. *Business horizons* 54: 241-251.
- Kim, Y. kim, M. & Kim, K. (2010). Factors influencing the adoption of social media in
- Ndaku, A.J (2013). Impact of social media on students’ academic performance-A study of students of university of Abuja. (an undergraduate project submitted to department of mass communication management and social sciences Caritas University.
- Rubin, A. (2002). Media uses and effects: A uses-and-gratifications perspective. In J.Bryant and D. Zillmann (Eds), *Media effects: Advances in theory and research* (pp. 417-436). New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc.
- Seyi, O. (2021). Social media and Nigeria Youth Burden. A paper presented in Blue Print Newspaper December 17 2012.
- Sofela, T. (2012). The effect of social media on students. A paper presented in craft magazine October 23 2012.
- Ufuophu, E. & Agobami, O. (2012). Usage of information and communication technologies and Job motivation among newspaper workers in Nigeria. *Journal of communication and Media Research*, 4(1).
- Mitchell, M. P. (2021). *Disadvantages of social networking: Surprising insights from teens*. Retrieved from <https://www.rootsofaction.com>
- Vanessa, R. (2021). *Advantages and disadvantages of social media for Students*. Retrieved from <https://blog.skillsuccess.com/advantages-and-disadvantages-of-social-media-for-students/>